

Optical dispersion in waveguides based upon the Pancharatnam-Berry phase

Stree Vithya Arumugam¹, Chandroth P. Jisha¹, Alessandro Alberucci¹, Stefan Nolte^{1,2}

1. Friedrich Schiller University, Institute of Applied Physics, Albert-Einstein-Str. 15, 07745, Jena, Germany

2. Fraunhofer Institute for Applied Optics and Precision Engineering IOF, Albert-Einstein-Str. 7, 07745, Jena, Germany

Optical waveguides usually exploit modulation of the dynamic phase, i.e., transverse gradient in the refractive index, to guide light. Recently, a novel type of optical waveguides based upon the Pancharatnam-Berry phase (PBP) has been introduced [1]. The PBP is a type of geometric phase which is determined by the path traced by the polarization on the Poincaré sphere. For example, PBP gained by a circularly polarized (CP) beam after crossing a half-wave plate (HWP) is twice the rotation angle of the crystal, the sign being dictated by the photon helicity [2]. Hence, an inhomogeneous rotation in the transverse plane induces a transverse phase gradient. However, the PBP does not accumulate in propagation if the structure is uniform along the longitudinal (propagation) direction. A net accumulation, and thus localization, is achieved when the anisotropic material is periodically perturbed along the propagation direction. The optimum is indeed attained when the longitudinal modulation is synchronized with the natural rotation of the polarization [1,3].

In this contribution we theoretically investigate the dependence of PBP waveguides on the optical wavelength, the latter being directly proportional to the birefringence length. By using a plane-wave model based upon the Jones calculus, we first show that the accumulated phase vanishes for mismatches of $\pm 50\%$ with respect to the synchronized case. FDTD (1+1)D simulations are carried out in a material of birefringence 0.2, first for a fixed wavelength and different longitudinal periods. The ansatz for the local rotation is a Gaussian distribution of width w_D and amplitude Γ_0 along the transverse plane, whereas a sinusoidal modulation is assumed along the propagation direction. As shown in Fig. 1(a-f), the confinement is robust, even if the fundamental structured mode undergoes appreciable variations. The FDTD simulations also show a better confinement in comparison with the predictions of the plane wave model. In the second step we excite the structure with optical pulses of different duration to investigate how the optical dispersion is affected by the phase-matching condition between the birefringence length and the longitudinal modulation. Interestingly, beyond the transverse distribution of the twisting angle, the dispersion depends on the wavelength position with respect to the resonance, the latter showing a Voigt-like line shape.

Fig. 1 (a-j) Intensity distribution of a quasi-mode (a-e) RCP, (f-j) LCP; propagating in a PBP waveguide with $w_D = 5 \mu m$, $\Gamma_0 = 15^\circ$ and different longitudinal modulation periods, as stated above each column.

In conclusion, we demonstrated the robustness of PBP waveguides away from the phase-matched case. The role of the synchronization condition on the waveguide dispersion is investigated. Potential future applications range from the polarization-shaping of optical pulses to the design of integrated stretchers and compressors.

References

- [1] S. Slussarenko, A. Alberucci, C.P. Jisha, B. Piccirillo, E. Santamato, G. Assanto, and L. Marrucci, "Guiding light via geometric phases," *Nat. Photon.* **10**, 571 (2016).
- [2] Z. Bomzon, G. Biener, V. Kleiner, and E. Hasman, "Space-variant Pancharatnam–Berry phase optical elements with computer-generated subwavelength gratings," *Opt. Lett.* **27**, 1141–1143 (2002).
- [3] C.P. Jisha, S. V. Arumugam, L. Marrucci, S. Nolte, and A. Alberucci, "Waveguiding driven by the Pancharatnam-Berry phase," *Phys. Rev. A* **107**, 013523 (2023)